

Author, Artist, Actress: China's New Women Cultural Entrepreneurs

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Abstract

Cutting across the boundaries of media, literature, visual arts, and cultural studies, this study examines the resurgence of cultural entrepreneurship in post-Mao China, focusing on how the new media have contributed to the rise of women cultural entrepreneurs as a new social phenomenon. It investigates the rise of China's women "cultural entrepreneurs" and their roles as tastemakers and cultural trendsetters, using three case studies from China's creative industries: author Anni Baobei, artist Cao Fei, and actress Xu Jinglei. The Chinese women cultural entrepreneurs are examined against the backdrop of the Reform-era history and growing importance of China's creative industries. Analysis explores how these entrepreneurs use the new media for content dissemination while spinning transmedia narratives about themselves. By examining female self-fashioning and the creation of the cultural entrepreneur as a new type of celebrity in China, the article aims to shed new light on the cultural and social negotiations in China's mediasphere.

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Keywords

Chinese literature, Chinese visual arts, Chinese media, Chinese Cultural Studies

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Introduction

The face of the future in the world of global business – according to Swiss artist Rosalina Battiston – is a Chinese female entrepreneur: specifically, a new type of Chief Executive Officer (CEO) or “Chinese female Executive Officer.” The title page of the 2011 *Magazin* supplement to the *Neue Zürcher Zeitung* on the theme “CEO: From Strategy to Entrepreneurial Success” provocatively featured Battiston’s portrait of a Chinese woman entitled, “Potential CEO of the Future: Chinese Female Executive Officer” (Hilb, 2011).

This study unravels the theme of the Chinese woman entrepreneur to examine the new roles of women emerging in China’s cultural industries. Spanning China’s post-socialist era between circa 1997 and 2023, this article uses media, literature, and cultural studies approaches to trace the rise of women cultural entrepreneurs in twenty-first-century China. Analysis focuses on three case studies: novelist Anni Baobei 安妮宝贝 (Annie Baby, b. 1974), visual artist Cao Fei 曹斐 (b. 1978), and movie celebrity Xu Jinglei 徐静蕾 (b. 1974). All three women belong to China’s Generation X or “brand-new mankind” (新新人类, *xinxin renlei*; Li, 2011: 59), who came of age in Deng Xiaoping’s Reform era (1978–present) with little or no personal memory of the Mao years.

To redress the dearth of studies on China’s women cultural entrepreneurs, this article examines the rise of women as literary entrepreneurs, multi-media celebrities, and avant-garde artists in China. It aims to contribute to the fields of global cultural history, media, literature, visual arts, urban studies, and gender studies, firstly, because it sharpens the focus on the new phenomenon of women rising to prominence in China’s creative industries, and secondly, because it sheds new light on this phenomenon not only in China’s megacities but also in the new cyberspace.

The resurgence of cultural entrepreneurship in today’s China stems from long-term government policies as well as socio-cultural changes. If the market-oriented reforms of the cultural sphere in the 1980s–1990s have sown the seeds of an entrepreneurial “creative class” (Florida, 2011), the emphasis placed by the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) on home-grown innovation and cultural creativity since 2006 has spurred its growth (Keane, 2013: 97–124). During this time, the Chinese cultural and media spheres have become increasingly diversified, market-oriented, and celebrity-centred (Guo, 2020; Kong, 2004).

The current configuration of cultural entrepreneurship in China is also linked to the characteristics of social media networks such as Sina Weibo 微博 and Tencent’s WeChat (or Weixin 微信 in China) as vehicles of creative expression, promotion, and branding that tend to elide any distinction between authorial personae and real-life human beings. While China has produced Internet celebrities (网红, *wanghong*) who owe their popularity to such technologies, this article argues that cultural entrepreneurs have woven their personae as commodified transmedia narratives (Jenkins et al., 2013: 138) across traditional media such as print literature and television as well as through

online infrastructures and genres such as WeChat and the blog. We shall discuss the definition and ramifications of the term “cultural entrepreneur” in more detail below.

Research on China’s creative industries has focused on relevant policies, such as the intellectual property regime (e.g. Montgomery, 2010) and investment in creative clusters (e.g. Keane, 2009), and examined the development of the art market and the design industry (e.g. Keane, 2016). A number of studies on this topic have analysed the cultural industries in certain cities, especially in Shanghai (e.g. Gu, 2014; White and Xu, 2012; Zhong, 2016). While this research shows the growing size and importance of the cultural industries in China, the role and influence of individual cultural entrepreneurs await further research. This study aims to fill this gap by focusing on an under-researched subject in studies of China’s cultural industries, namely women cultural entrepreneurs.

Rising to prominence in the 1980s, the figure of the woman entrepreneur in what was then called China’s “commodity economy” (商品经济, *shangpin jingji*) represented a post-socialist metamorphosis of the model worker, as early discussions of the topic reveal (e.g. Ni and Qian, 1987; Qiu and Li, 1985). In 1985, the China Association of Women Entrepreneurs was established under the supervision of the Ministry of Civil Affairs and in 1988 surveys counted 7000 women entrepreneurs in Guangdong province and 700 in Beijing (Hisrich and Fan, 1991: 8). By 2012 women reportedly accounted for a quarter of the total number of entrepreneurs in China (Wong, 2012), that is, an estimated 29 million (see Welsh et al., 2017: 175). The stories of women entrepreneurs have tended to complicate two prevailing narratives on women and gender in Reform-era China, namely, the official narrative, which asserts that government policies have improved the condition of Chinese women and promoted gender equality, citing the growing number of women entrepreneurs as evidence of this (e.g. People’s Daily Online, 2014) and the opposite narrative, which maintains that the reforms have eroded the supposed gender equality of the socialist era (1949–1978) and victimised women, particularly working women and women living in the countryside (e.g. Chen, 2011: 2; cf. Attané, 2012). Blalock and Lyu’s (2023) recent study of narratives of female entrepreneurship in official Chinese media points at the lingering tension between these narratives, as the ideal woman entrepreneur – or, “*patriot-preneur*,” to use a term coined by the authors – is expected to strive towards success in business while at the same time taking care of her family, honouring her country, and contributing to the collective fate of Chinese women. Since the 1980s, female entrepreneurialism has therefore shown the opportunities – or coping strategies – offered by the reforms and globalisation, but also revealed persisting obstacles and new barriers to emancipation and equality.

As far as the cultural industries are concerned, while studies such as Oakley (2013) and Gill (2014, 2018) have addressed the gender aspect of cultural entrepreneurialism and the condition of women in this sector in Anglo-American contexts, studies that focus on women in China’s cultural industries remain rare (e.g. Chow, 2019). In one such study, Wang and Keane (2020) examined the stories of sixteen women entrepreneurs in the digital creative industries and found that women in this sector have to contend with a “gendered culture of technology and entrepreneurship” (Wang and Keane, 2020: 416) that hinders their access to business opportunities and traditional

gender roles, as well as the precarious condition of creative work in today's China. Wang and Keane (2020: 419) also point out the need for more research on the "evolving relationship between individual and collective female entrepreneurial identity," and it is hoped that this study will contribute to filling this gap.

Women "have played key roles" in China's cultural and creative industries (Wang and Keane, 2020: 408), while women entrepreneurs have dominated new sectors such as e-commerce and the billion-dollar live-streaming industry (McCarthy, 2017; Zhang and Miller, 2017). In the first decade of the twenty-first century, the blog run by actress, film director, and magazine editor Xu Jinglei – one of the main figures discussed in this study – was the most visited in the world until the rise to stardom of novelist, blogger and film-maker Han Han 韩寒 (b. 1982) (see Strafella and Berg, 2015). In the 2010s, one of China's most successful Internet celebrities was female comedian and video blogger Papi Jiang (Papi 酱, also known as Jiang Yilei 姜逸磊, b. 1987). Papi Jiang turned online celebrity into a profitable business despite being criticised by the authorities for being foul-mouthed and "vulgar" (Meijing, 2016; Xinhua, 2016). More recently, video blogger Li Ziqi 李子柒 (b. 1990) achieved national and international stardom with short videos that portray an idealised and stylish version of Chinese rural life. Official party media praised her for producing cultural commodities that alleviate the mental health problems resulting from modern life (People's Daily Online, 2019) and for becoming a successful Chinese cultural export (Li, 2020), while at the same time commercial video platform Youku 优酷 placed Li Ziqi at the top of a list of Internet superstars with the highest commercial value (Youku, 2019).

Thanks to video-sharing platforms, Internet celebrities have emerged even from the world of higher education, to provide self-help and "moral" education, as the case of Fudan University lecturer Chen Guo 陈果 (b. 1981) exemplifies (see Marco Fumian's article in this special issue). Another academic celebrity who has provided similar content to an even larger audience is media scholar Yu Dan 于丹 (b. 1965), who established herself through traditional media – including official television channels and prestigious print publishers – before expanding to online platforms. Yu Dan was once ranked as the second highest-earning author in the country (People's Daily Online, 2012) while working as a professor of Media Studies at Beijing Normal University and serving as a member of the Eighteenth National Congress of the CCP from 2012 to 2016. Her Sina blog attracted over two million visits, despite being active for a mere two months in 2007; her verified Weibo account (ID: yudan) has well over three million followers and mainly features information about her public activities, photos from her travels, and (more recently) links to posts on her official WeChat channel (ID: BNU-YUDAN). On WeChat, Yu Dan publishes advice on how to live successfully and contentedly, alongside stock photos of natural landscapes. The mediatic evolution of Yu Dan's philosopher persona points to a major characteristic of women cultural entrepreneurs in today's China which is discussed in this study, namely their ability to cross between more prestigious, traditional, and established mediatic spaces and the new commercial digital media, and thus weave transmedia narratives of both their own selves and their cultural enterprises.

The first part of this article discusses the concept of the cultural entrepreneur and proposes a theoretical framework that foregrounds the politico-cultural significance of this figure in Reform-era China. The second part analyses the origins of cultural entrepreneurialism in present-day Chinese society and discusses the usage of this term in China's official media discourse, placing it in the context of the cultural industries and a celebrity-centred mediasphere. This part highlights the complex status of women cultural entrepreneurs in twentieth-century China by pointing to their relative marginality in the politico-ideological sphere but their centrality in the socio-cultural sphere. The third part of the article identifies key features of cultural entrepreneurship by examining the cases of three examples of successful women cultural entrepreneurs – a literary author, a visual artist, and an actress, film and television celebrity.

The Cultural Entrepreneur: A Conceptual Framework

To provide a conceptual framework for its analysis of women cultural entrepreneurs in China, this study proceeds from the observation that a definition of cultural entrepreneurship should acknowledge its political and ideological dimensions, as well as its economic one. With regard to entrepreneurship in East Asian popular culture, Otmazgin has shown that “popular culture entrepreneurs not only generate value in the economic sense, but also value in terms of feelings, identification, and perceptions”; they disseminate “ideas, emotions and sensibilities” while they “construct mechanisms for commodifying and marketing popular culture” (Otmazgin, 2011: 264). As to how cultural entrepreneurs influence cultural change, Aageson, who defines the cultural entrepreneur as “one who creates cultural value and wealth for the creators and producers of cultural products and services,” views the cultural entrepreneur as a “change agent,” but also as someone who can enhance and sustain traditions and values (Aageson, 2008: 92–96). While cultural entrepreneurs may influence beliefs and customs in a transformative as well as a conservative fashion, examples from China's early modern and contemporary history (see e.g. Berg, 2013; Berg, 2000) suggest that the very existence of women cultural entrepreneurs undermines conservative gender roles in China to some extent, including the officially sanctioned stigmatisation of professional and career-oriented women (To, 2015: 27).

In addition, this article draws on Joel Mokyr's (2013) definition of the cultural entrepreneur as it focuses on an ideological dimension. Mokyr (2013: 2) defines the cultural entrepreneur as someone who adds to the “menu” of beliefs and cultural preferences from which others choose. If culture is “a system of beliefs, values, and preferences,” Mokyr argues, “for a small number of individuals, the beliefs of others are not given but can be changed” (Mokyr, 2013: 2). Citing Francis Bacon and Isaac Newton as examples, this economic historian views cultural entrepreneurs as playing a role analogous to that of entrepreneurs in the realm of production, in that they “refuse to take the existing technology or market structure as given and try to change it and ... benefit personally in the process” (Mokyr, 2013: 2). This study will not scrutinise the Bacons and Newtons of today's China, but focuses on

figures who, by changing the cultural–ideological menu, can shape the tastes and values of their consumers.

Finally, inspired by what Elizabeth Currid wrote in 1970s–1980s New York in her book *The Warhol Economy*, this study sheds light on the tastemakers and gatekeepers of China’s cultural economy. The figure of the cultural entrepreneur occupies the “intersection of culture and cash” (Currid, 2007: 37), and highlights “the importance of the social component to cultural production” (Currid, 2007: 34). Naudin (2018: 133–161) has similarly shown how real-life networking and virtual interaction help cultural entrepreneurs build and magnify their creative and entrepreneurial personae. Furthermore, Currid (2007) underscored how such figures, besides exchanging cultural goods, attain “star” status by publicising their lifestyle through sustained media exposure. This study analogously identifies an overlapping between cultural entrepreneurship and celebrity culture, shedding light on how cultural entrepreneurs employ media exposure and social networking to shape and promote their personal brands.

Cultural Entrepreneurialism in Reform-Era China

One finds modern antecedents to contemporary Chinese cultural entrepreneurs in early twentieth-century China. As Christopher Rea and Nicolai Volland have shown, mobility between cultural professions and participation in multiple modes of cultural production characterised cultural entrepreneurship in an era in which the production and consumption of culture changed dramatically (Rea, 2015: 10; Rea and Volland, 2015: 3). One type of pre-1949 cultural entrepreneur identified by Rea is the “cultural personality,” that is, an individual who creates their own cultural products and whose “personal brand attracts customers across multiple cultural spheres” (Rea, 2015: 18). Women cultural entrepreneurs in post-Mao China have also participated in multiple cultural spheres at a time when the tastes and values of Chinese citizens and customers have become increasingly diverse, as this study will show.

Today’s cultural entrepreneurs represent a by-product of the introduction of market principles and commercial dynamics into the socio-cultural sphere after the beginning of Reform and Opening-up in 1978, and especially since the early 1990s. At that time, artists and literary authors who joined the nationwide “jump into the sea” of business (下海, *xia hai*) met with the scorn of many in the cultural establishment. For instance, Zhang Xianliang 张贤亮 (1936–2014) was one of China’s most celebrated authors of literature that reflected on the tragedies of the Maoist era. The literary and academic establishment looked askance as his public figure shifted from cultural cadre and lofty-minded intellectual to CEO of a commercial film studio in the early 1990s (Lu, 2007: 50). Around the same time, Wang Shuo 王朔 (b. 1958) became one of the first freelance authors who rejected the manuscript fees of the socialist literary system and negotiated with publishers on the market value of their writing (Kong, 2004: 28). As Wang Shuo became a best-selling novelist by the end of the 1980s, in the eyes of the state he remained merely one of the “financially independent unemployed” (Barmé, 1999: 70). Zhang Xianliang

and Wang Shuo heralded the re-emergence of Chinese cultural entrepreneurship in the Reform era.

It is worth remembering that a factor allowing for the rise of cultural entrepreneurs from the late 1990s to 2012 was the expansion of state-enforced boundaries between tolerated speech and sensitive topics, especially on the Internet (Herold, 2008). As a result, China witnessed the rise to prominence of people who “pushed” those boundaries, especially where they remained vaguely defined or were erratically enforced (Stern and O’Brien, 2012). Starting with a crackdown on prominent micro-bloggers in 2013, Xi Jinping has all but put an end to this trend by increasing the danger of pursuing commercial success by means of “spectacular rebellion” (Strafella and Berg, 2015) against ideological orthodoxy.

Meanwhile, the CCP’s goal of turning the country into a cultural superpower (e.g. Lee, 2018: 4; People’s Daily Online, 2018a) caters to an even older nationalist yearning that stems from the modern Chinese intellectual tradition. Both economic policy and political rhetoric reflect this aspiration. In particular, the emphasis on home-grown innovation since the Eleventh Five-Year Plan (2006–2010) has spurred the growth of the cultural industries and cultural entrepreneurship. China’s central authorities have sought to develop the national creative and cultural industries into a “pillar” sector of the economy, ordering state-owned cultural enterprises to grow in both size and profitability. At the same time, they have instructed all players in the field of cultural production and distribution – including private companies – to deliver “social benefits” and promote “core socialist values” through their activities (Ministry of Culture, 2017). However, Beijing only partially reformed the cultural industries to allow or force them to function in a market economy, since “cultural public service work units” retained a propaganda function and therefore could not be fully privatised (Chang, 2009: 267; cf. Keane, 2013: 4). The effort to balance commercialisation and political imperatives has been described as “controlled commodification” (Weber and Jia, 2007). In a context where a party-controlled framework existed within an imperfect market environment, the dominance of that framework was challenged by cultural entrepreneurs “empowered by powerful consumers demanding creative content without state interference” (Chang, 2009: 264).

The 1990s saw the popularisation of the term “cultural entrepreneur” (文化企业家, *wenhua qiyejia*), which was used even to describe figures of the past such as the scholar-official and publisher Zhang Yuanji 张元济 (1867–1959) (Xu, 1997). The term has caught on in recent years to denote founders and executives of companies in the cultural industries and, more often, any individual involved in the commercialisation of cultural products (e.g. Liu, 2016). Signalling the adoption of the term in official discourse, from 2012 until 2019 the *Guangming Daily* embraced it to describe individuals selected annually as the top “personalities of the Chinese cultural industries.” The official press appears to employ the term mainly to denote the leaders of commercial enterprises involved in film production, video games, online literature, theatre, and so on (e.g. He, 2016). The compilation of the list in the *Guangming Daily*, carried out under the leadership of China’s Propaganda Department (Zhang and Chen, 2014), reflects how the politico-

cultural establishment views individuals who aim to extract maximum market value from culture and suggests a policy of control and co-optation vis-à-vis private-sector cultural industry entrepreneurs. It is noteworthy that out of the thirty candidates shortlisted for the “Cultural Industries Personality of the Year” award in 2018 only four were women, including film director Wang Chao 王潮歌 (b. 1965) and the CEOs of three media and entertainment corporations (Zi et al., 2018). The 2018 winner of the accolade was a man, Cheng Wu 程武, vice-president of Tencent Holdings and CEO of Tencent Pictures (People’s Daily Online, 2018b). Since 2021, the newspaper has compiled an annual list of the top thirty cultural enterprises rather than entrepreneurs (Xinhua, 2021).

Besides highlighting a gender disparity at the top of cultural enterprises, the *Guangming Daily* honours highlight a key difference between the working definition of cultural entrepreneur proposed by this study and the one that emerges from the above-mentioned activities of the Propaganda Department. That is, the “cultural industries personalities” selected by the *Guangming Daily* have included few actual “creatives.” These lists feature mainly industry tycoons such as Li Guoqing 李国庆 (b. 1964), founder of China’s top online bookstore Dangdang.com, or real estate magnate Wang Jianlin 王健林 (b. 1956), whose ranking among China’s top cultural entrepreneurs stems from his Wanda Group’s involvement in film production and ownership of cinemas across the world.

The lavish celebration of these “cultural entrepreneurs” might show that Beijing has “discovered the value of the individual, creative self-expression and grassroots energy in transforming Chinese economy and society,” as Wang (2016: 59) put it. Not every cultural entrepreneur views culture and creativity as compatible with co-optation by the party-state, however, and the authorities will not embrace just any type of creative self-expression. Ai Weiwei 艾未未 (b. 1957), arguably one of the most globally influential and controversial Chinese cultural entrepreneurs, wrote in *The New York Times* that “managers of artistic and cultural projects ... need to show proactively that they ‘get it’ and will accommodate the authoritarians and protect their public image. They know that if anything causes unhappiness higher up, a project, and perhaps an organisation, will be scrubbed” (Ai, 2017). Ai Weiwei considers himself a “businessman” but stresses the importance of upholding certain “values around the business” (in König, 2020). Lily Chumley’s research on Chinese art schools also highlighted the tension existing today between the global commodity culture, the nationalistic utopia of China as a cultural superpower, and the cultural creator’s pursuit of aesthetic values that transcend the market (Chumley, 2016).

Finally, our definition of cultural entrepreneur points to the link between cultural entrepreneurialism and celebrity. Research on celebrity in Reform-era China has shown the diverse nature of its construction and manifestation and its complex interaction with official discourses (Edwards and Jeffreys, 2010). In this era, China has created celebrities who sold “both products and inspiration to a new generation of aspiring young people and future (world) leaders” (Jeffreys, 2012: 26). Research on celebrity-centred philanthropy and activism also suggested that Chinese celebrities could become a “force for social change” in the country, “given the limited spaces available for

broader political participation in that country” (Jeffreys, 2016: 773). Chinese media have promoted celebrity entrepreneurs not only as a model of how to navigate the Reform-era economy, but also as living lessons of morality and discipline for the entire society (Davies, 2010). As argued by a study on women celebrities in Chinese cinema, the economic value of their celebrity status is closely linked to the socio-cultural values they convey, their ability to resonate with and influence the mindset of their audiences, and how their femininity is performed and received (Chen and Pan, 2008).

On the other hand, the Chinese celebrity industry – not unlike other (culture) industries in the country – operates within an interlinked commercial, technological, legal, and political structure (Sullivan and Kehoe, 2019). To begin with, the influence of commercial popular culture and social media has led to celebrities becoming part of China’s governance, as some politicians have acquired celebrity status while some celebrities from commercial entertainment and sports participate in the National People’s Congress and the Chinese People’s Consultative Conference. Party-state authorities have acknowledged the influence of celebrities on society, and have explicitly set out norms and expectations with regard to how celebrities behave in public as well as to cultural products (Sullivan and Kehoe, 2019: 245). Sullivan and Kehoe have shown how party-state and industrial actors fabricated celebrities that could stand as exemplars of “model behaviour” including “middle class” and “traditional” values, patriotism, and “acceptance of the political regime” (Sullivan and Kehoe, 2019: 252). Besides endorsing products, celebrities endorse the CCP, too, for instance by attending highly publicised meetings to study the party line, or simply by praising the achievements of CCP-ruled China. Legitimation also flows the other way around. The portrayal of super-rich celebrities as morally upright, hardworking, and politically sound reassures China’s middle class that the most conspicuous “winners” in their highly unequal society deserve their privilege and status. One might therefore argue that the narrative of celebrity virtue accompanied by stern official criticism of “immoral,” law-breaking and “vulgar” celebrities (see the example of Papi Jiang, above) – benefits the legitimacy of the socio-political status quo.

Clearly, the categories of celebrity and cultural entrepreneur do not overlap entirely. Many celebrities do not engage in creative work, or they are better described as the products of, rather than agents within, the media industry (e.g. Rojek, 2001), as in the case of “idols” in today’s China (Hao, 2019). However, this study will show that the success of cultural entrepreneurs in China stems not only from their association with successful cultural commodities, but also from their ability to navigate celebrity culture and mould their own public persona into a “cultural commodity.”

Women Cultural Entrepreneurs: Three Case Studies

The next sections will analyse the works of three women – a literary author, a visual artist, and an actress, film and television celebrity – who have achieved remarkable success as cultural entrepreneurs in their respective fields while shaping their public personae across multiple media. This analysis will bring to light some of the features that characterise cultural entrepreneurship in twenty-first-century China, including the inter-relationship

between the traditional and the new media; the “co-optation” of avant-garde languages into market-oriented cultural industries; and the transmediality of both cultural products and the cultural entrepreneurs themselves.

The Literary Author

Li Jie 励婕 (b. 1974) first became widely known as a literary author using the pen name of Anni Baobei. Her multiple personae epitomise the many facets of today’s creative and celebrity industries. One of China’s first Internet writers, Anni Baobei began publishing her works on the literary website Under the Banyan Tree (榕树下, *Rongshu xia*) in 1998. At the time, Li Jie was working in banking and advertising, but she later joined the staff of Under the Banyan Tree – one of China’s earliest venues for literary Internet publishing – and published a regular column on this website starting in 2000. There, Anni Baobei promoted her fictional and auto-biographical writings “for kindred spirits to read,” as a statement next to her photo on the column’s homepage read, thus creating “the illusion of direct contact between author and reader” (Hockx, 2015: 39).

Also in 2000, Anni Baobei published her first volume in print, *Goodbye, Vivian* (告别薇安, *Gaobie Wei'an*), a collection of short stories that included some of the works she had previously published online. Following her print debut, she abandoned online writing to become an established *author* (作家, *zuojia*), a writer whose prestige arises from publishing in the traditional print media, as opposed to an “Internet hack” (写手, *xieshou*):

I began writing with a very playful attitude, just having fun online, writing stories as if I were playing games. Then I realised that when these stories became available online, many people enjoyed reading them, and that is why they were eventually published in print. Once my work had begun to be published in print, starting from 2000, I simply stopped posting my works online. Everything changed then, because my print books found many readers and I turned into a proper professional writer. Print has become the main publishing avenue for me now. I don’t see any difference between these two kinds of media. (Interview with the authors, Beijing, 1 September 2014; all translations from Chinese are by the authors unless otherwise indicated.)

Goodbye, Vivian went on to sell an estimated half a million copies and turned her into a household name among young readers. Between circa 2009 and 2013, Anni Baobei ranked among the highest-earning authors in the country (e.g. Ifeng, 2013).

The short story “Goodbye, Vivian” in the eponymous collection presents a prominent example of how Anni Baobei packages her work as a luxury product for the young urban consumer in the new digital age. It dramatises the fate of two lovers – the principal male protagonist Lin 林 and his love object, a mysterious Internet presence who identifies herself as a person called Vivian. They only ever meet in an online chatroom in cyberspace and inhabit the anonymity of China’s new megacities such as Shanghai or another unspecified city “over one thousand *li* (Chinese miles) further north” and “by the sea” with “houses built in the Western style” (Anni, 2008: 10). The implied other

city is never named, but appears to allude to Qingdao 青岛 in Shandong 山东 province, with its distinct German-style redbrick buildings and the remnants of its past as a former German colony. Yet the cityscape forms only a backdrop to an online drama that could unfold anywhere in new digital China. The anonymity of the postmodern megacity extends into that of cyberspace.

The name Vivian first appears in the Latin alphabet, marking it as exotic and Western, much like May Fourth writer Ding Ling's 丁玲 (1904–1986) heroine in her short story "Miss Sophia's Diary" (莎菲女士的日记, *Shafei nüshi riji*, 1928). Yet unlike Sophia, Vivian also appears as the Chinese name Weiwei'an 薇薇安 and Wei'an 薇安, alluding to the multiple identities of the main female protagonist. Tragedy unfolds in Lin's ill-fated search for Vivian's identity, the thwarting of his desire and the confusion this inflicts on him. The narrator highlights the theme of lost identities in the new urban jungle and the maze of cyberspace in the opening paragraph:

He has no clue where she is. That's just as well. She might appear at any moment. It's so easy to get lost in this game right from the start. He has no clue whether that's the nature of the game or whether it's part of the secret between him and her. (Anni, 2008: 1)

Vivian appears in at least two guises: first, as Cyber-Vivian who claims to live in an anonymous city up north by the sea but only exists online; and second, as Metro-Vivian, a metropolitan young woman Lin encounters at an unnamed Shanghai Metro station. Lin only addresses her as "An," revealing the third persona of Vivian as the implied author Anni Baobei by using the first character (An) of Li Jie's pen name.

The protagonists appear as young urban professionals in their twenties who may live in any of China's new megacities. A graphic designer working for an advertising company in Shanghai, Metro-Vivian shows semi-autobiographical traits of Li Jie. As mentioned above, the author too worked for an advertising company during her stay in Shanghai in her early twenties. The protagonists' online chats portray the characters as faceless individuals caught in a web of loneliness, alienation, social isolation, and feelings of doom and gloom. Their identities remain shrouded in mystery and lost in cyberspace to the extent that they can neither recognise each other when they meet nor identify other people when they meet them. Instead, Lin assigns wishful identities to the women he meets online and offline and sees the Vivian of his chats and dreams in every girl in the city.

Like their fluid identities, the protagonists' online language ranges from "simple" to "enigmatic" (Anni, 2008: 2). The unobtrusive narrator even blurs the female protagonists' identities – first, Lin's bloodless cyber-lover Vivian, whom the narrator adorns with the identity of his dream girl by calling her An; second, Lin's flesh-and-blood lover Qiao whom he exploits physically to satisfy his desires but for whom he feels no emotions; and third, the office girl Lin meets in the Shanghai Metro station who calls herself Vivian.

Lin believes Metro-Vivian to be the Cyber-Vivan of his online chat, but Cyber-Vivian later reveals that she does not live in Shanghai but in another anonymous city far up north by the sea, a likely reference to Qingdao, as mentioned above. Neither the protagonists

nor the reader can ever be sure of the characters' identities. Even the protagonists' physical encounter cannot provide conclusive evidence.

The narrator reveals that Cyber-Vivian dresses in white cotton, but Metro-Vivian dresses in a black shirt and blue jeans; both female characters are described as "cool" and "aloof," reflecting Li Jie's image as a cool and aloof author in her persona as Anni Baobei. Like her protagonists, the author's style of communicating with her readers ranges from simple to enigmatic. She appears in photo shoots dressed exclusively in simple natural linen fabrics, limited to the colours white, black and blue.

In this way, Li Jie has succeeded in fashioning her personal style as a literary brand, as advised by her publisher Lu Jinbo 路金波 (b. 1975) – who had already gained fame by promoting the novelists Han Han and Guo Jingming 郭敬明 (b. 1983) to super-stardom, marketing them as literary celebrities. During her rise to fame, Li Jie consolidated her exclusive literary brand as a luxury product and maintained her aloofness by refusing to appear in public or give interviews. In line with this, Lu Jinbo insisted that her books would only be published in luxury hardcover editions to maintain their exclusive appeal (in Martinsen, 2007).

After publishing several novels under the name of Anni Baobei, among them *Lotus* (莲花, *Lianhua*, 2006), the author announced via Weibo in 2014 that she would adopt the Buddhist-inspired pen name Qingshan 庆山. Li Jie, now a member of the Chinese Writers Association, explained to her followers that "Anni Baobei" would not disappear, but "like a tree growing a new branch, or a traveller walking up to another border," her old identity would "dissolve" into the new one (Zhang, 2014). Shortly after the announcement, her publisher Lu Jinbo announced that Anni Baobei's bestselling works would be re-published under her new pen name (Zhang, 2014). Her Weibo account (ID: anepadma), now named "Qingshan/Anni Baobei," has over 10 million followers and promotes Qingshan as a Buddhist-inspired traveller through philosophical musings about life, meditative photos of landscapes and objects, and occasionally links to purchase her new Qingshan-authored books. One easily notices how Li Jie's Weibo fuses her former pen name Anni Baobei with her new Buddhism-inspired persona – the lotus flower, *padma* in Sanskrit, one of Buddhism's eight auspicious symbols. This cultural entrepreneur has thus reinvented herself for a new audience while catching on to yet another cultural trend of post-socialist China, that is, the ongoing religious-spiritual revival in the context of secular modernity and capitalism. Writing under her two pen names, Li Jie has so far published at least fifteen books and many more short stories – including a 2019 novella in one of China's most prestigious literary magazines, *Harvest* (收获, *Shouhuo*) – while at the same time working as a translator, columnist, and editor of a literary magazine.

Li Jie's switch from online writing to traditional publishing – accompanied by the adoption of blogging and social media – highlights the new material and symbolic relations between traditional and online media in today's cultural sphere. As mentioned with reference to Anni Baobei, in the early first decade of the twenty-first century writers of Internet literature achieved the coveted status of a literary author by moving from online publishing to the more prestigious world of printed books. However, during the

last two decades the literary establishment – from the Chinese Writers Association to literary prizes – has become open to granting institutional recognition to Internet literature (Zhao, 2019), while the circulation of stories, characters, and authorial personae between online and traditional media has become central to the production and consumption of culture in the country. In today’s literary industry, the old hierarchy of prestige between online and print media has been subsumed without disappearing in a functional integration of these realms, while complex interactions between multiple traditional and digital media have emerged in both the promotion and the production of the cultural entrepreneur’s creations.

The Visual Artist

Cao Fei is one of China’s most successful multi-media artists and a celebrity in the international art world. She has twice won Chinese Contemporary Art Awards (Best Young Artist, 2006, and Best Artist, 2016), prizes established by the Swiss cultural entrepreneur and businessman Uli Sigg (b. 1946). In 2020, she was the recipient of the Deutsche Börse Grand Prize (2021) for her solo exhibition *Blueprints* at London’s Serpentine Gallery. Commenting on the Deutsche Börse award, a recent article in a Chinese journal noted how Cao Fei’s artistic experimentation with digital art, photography, and video over a period of twenty years invites the audience to reflect on how technological and social development shapes our understanding of reality and how to respond to this reality with poetic sensibility (Chen, 2021: 109).

Starting from her earliest video and photographic artworks (e.g. *Imbalance 257*, 1999), Cao Fei’s art has displayed a connection with the rebelliousness of youth culture – from cosplayers (e.g. *A Mirage*, 2004) and hip hop (*Hip Hop: Guangzhou*, 2003) to the dreams of young factory workers (*My Future is not a Dream*, 2006; *Asia One*, 2018) – while also exploring the imaginative possibilities offered by the newest digital technologies such as virtual and augmented reality (e.g. *RMB City*, 2009–2011; *Trade Eden*, 2019). Cao Fei states that her role as an artist consists in observing, rather than critiquing China’s societal and cultural transformation (in *Bloomberg News*, 2016). Her art arguably does so from a detached and often satirical standpoint through “micro-narrative” (Fok, 2011) storytelling. Once called the most representative artist of her generation by *Southern People Weekly* (Wei, 2008), Cao Fei has declared that artists born after 1980 are “more cartoonish and less critical” and unconcerned with important events, preferring to “wallow in the whispers of their own little worlds” (in Duan, 2016: 138).

Cao Fei’s art frequently touches upon some of the major themes of contemporary critical art from China – such as the destructive consequences of urbanisation, the plight of migrant workers, and the “nationwide carnival of consumption” (Hou, 2018: 49). However, much of Cao Fei’s art seems centred around the artist herself, from her avatar Tracy as the protagonist of *RMB City*, the demolition of her studio in *Rumba II: Nomad* (2015), and her apartment complex as the setting of *Haze and Fog* (2013), to her acting in videos such as *Isle of Instability* (2020). Her self-promotional use of

social media – aimed at a mainland audience (via WeChat and Weibo) as well as an international one (via Instagram and Twitter) – contributes to shaping her artistic storytelling while at the same time projecting her image as a global artistic celebrity and offering fragments of her quotidian, including food and family life.

Cao Fei's activities embody the commercial dimension of contemporary Chinese art – in terms of both capital and destination – to an extent that justifies speaking of her as a successful entrepreneur in the art industry. The list of global corporations and brands that have commissioned her art during the last decade includes Deutsche Bank (*Three Days Treatment*, 2011), Gucci (*Rumba II: Nomad*), Louis Vuitton (*A Conversation – Sound Talk*, with Zafka Zhang, 2016), Apple (*Trade Eden*, 2019), and Audemars Piguet (*Isle of Instability*). Cao Fei's multimedia project *Unmanned – BMW Art Car #18* (2017), commissioned by the Bavarian automobile manufacturer and centred around their cars, intertwines references to Buddhist religiosity and virtual reality in a striking fusion of artistic experimentation and corporate promotion. The prominence of the commercial dimension in the activities of Chinese artists such as Cao Fei occasionally provokes the scorn of art critics. When commenting on Cao Fei's artworks *The Eternal Wave* (2020) and *Nova* (2019) as part of the exhibition *Mirage: Contemporary Art in Augmented Reality* (2020–2021) at the Ullens Center for Contemporary Art (UCCA) in Beijing, art historian Song Meng 宋蒙 (b. 1975) of the Chinese Academy of Art wrote:

When one looks into UCCA's business model with regard to contemporary art, the profit motive and commercial logic behind its exhibitions and programming are easily revealed. ... The fusion of art and commerce represents an inescapable issue in the development of Chinese contemporary art and commercial interests clearly drive and harness this development. The UCCA's current foray into the public sphere inevitably demonstrates such commercial ambition. (Song, 2021: 44)

Experimental and anti-establishment Chinese art that originated from the margins of the art world has enjoyed visibility and success in the globalised art market since at least the late 1990s. The case of Cao Fei's artistic enterprise demonstrates how China's cultural industries have fully integrated exploitation of avant-garde languages and commentary on modern trends into the logic of the market, especially when they gear their products towards Western markets. Such development also reflects a complete breakdown of the traditional distinction between “serious” or elite culture on the one hand, and hyper-commercialised pop culture on the other hand. Hence, provided they stay within the limits of politically acceptable public discourses, cultural entrepreneurs such as Cao Fei can successfully combine experimental art forms and “edgy” topics with intensive commercialisation and celebrity-centred social media promotion.

The Movie Star

The quintessential celebrity-cum-cultural-entrepreneur of Reform-era China, Xu Jinglei has appeared in many roles during her twenty-five-year career in the cultural industries

as a popular actress, writer, blogger, magazine editor, award-winning film and television director, and founder of a publishing company. The works and public personae of Xu Jinglei also show how cultural entrepreneurs cater to the market for values and lifestyles with transmedia narratives that cut across their cultural products and their publicly consumed “private” lives. The “Xu Jinglei phenomenon” indeed originated from the intermingling of her personality and personal life with her film roles (Cai, 2017: 67). Through their careers as portrayed in the news and social media, as well as through more traditional cultural commodities such as books and films, celebrity cultural entrepreneurs such as Xu Jinglei come to embody and commercially exploit the new values and consumerist aspirations of China’s middle class.

In the case of Xu Jinglei, this especially applies to the representation and the roles of women in urban China. Based on an analysis of the films Xu Jinglei has both directed and starred in, Vanderstaay (2019: 64–68) found that she has reacted against regressive notions of gender and challenged traditional tropes through the female protagonists who populate her films as much as she has done through her public personae. Capable of doing so without transgressing mainstream middle-class values, Xu Jinglei’s heroines in films such as *Letter from an Unknown Woman* (一个陌生女人的来信, *Yi ge mosheng nüren de laixin*, 2004) “act as mirror images for her in their attitude to marriage and sexuality” (Vanderstaay, 2019: 70; see also Zheng, 2015: 199–202). Xu Jinglei’s attempt to transpose the unnamed character of Stefan Zweig’s 1922 novel *Letter from an Unknown Woman* into a Chinese context suggests a parallel with Xu’s own “proclivity and beliefs” as “a self-determining woman who disregards old-fashioned ethical constraints and governs her own life course” (Cai, 2017: 73).

Xu Jinglei’s films, such as *Go Lala Go!* (杜拉拉升职记, *Du Lala shengzhiji*, 2011), feature representations of strong, independent, and successful women. They associate an aspirational middle-class lifestyle of luxury brands and mainstream beauty ideals (Cai, 2014: 3) with moral principles and norms of behaviour that dovetail with the interests of both the party-state and the corporate world (Fumian, 2016). Publishers and authors of books such as Li Ke 李可, on whose best-selling novel *Chronicle of Du Lala’s Promotion* (2007) Xu’s film was based, have marketed such “workplace novels” as being both realistic, because they reflect their authors’ life experiences, and useful sources of practical advice for real-life situations in which their readers may find themselves (Gonseth, 2017: 170–171). Chinese media scholars have for years debated the feminist quality of Xu Jinglei’s films and characters, as some contend that they visualise women’s aspirations for equality and empowerment (e.g. Yang, 2018). Others have drawn on post-feminist critique to argue that Xu Jinglei’s audience-pleasing celebration of “power girls” only pays lip service to emancipation, while in fact it reproduces repressive notions of beauty and fashion (Huang, 2013).

Yet Xu has also used films she directed, such as *Dreams May Come* (梦想照进现实, *Mengxiang zhaojin xianshi*, 2006), to respond to rumours about her romantic life (Cai, 2017: 69). A similar, albeit less sophisticated and value-laden web of allusions between the cultural entrepreneur’s life and the films they have directed appears in Han Han’s feature film *The Continent* (后会无期, *Hou hui wu qi*, 2014) (Strafella and

Berg, 2015: 353). One cannot but wonder to what extent Xu's example inspired the novelist-turned-racing car driver to follow in her famous footsteps.

This game of reflections and refractions relies on the audience's simultaneous awareness of the media that they accept as fictional – such as films, books, and television series – and the media that purport to represent real life, such as news, gossip, and most importantly, the star's self-fashioning by means of blogging and other social media. From Ai Weiwei (Strafella and Berg, 2018) to Guo Jingming (Kunze, 2017), Chinese cultural entrepreneurs have employed intermediality and transmediality to weave narratives of the fictional and the real across a diverse range of media, relying on each medium's specific strengths. Xu Jinglei has similarly resorted to transmedia storytelling to fashion her public personae, using both the traditional and the new digital media such as blogging (Guo, 2020: 104–105). In such media constructs, fictional storytelling appears “spread” across different media. The cultural entrepreneur's very public personae – or “personal brands” – emerge from transmedia self-fashioning practices that blur the boundaries between art and life. As described by Currid (2007), celebrities-cum-cultural entrepreneurs thus sell their lifestyles – here taken to denote models of private and public behaviour – alongside cultural commodities. As a Chinese commentator put it, the best character Xu Jinglei has ever played is Xu Jinglei herself (Lei, 2015).

In the age of social media, real-time news, and reality television, such transmedia storytelling woven across fiction and reality results in levelling the distinctions between the flesh-and-blood Empirical Author living in our world, the Model Author who emerges from a work of fiction and is immanent to this work (Eco, 1994: 14–25), and the fictional protagonists. In this case study, Xu Jinglei appears prominently in all three roles – first, she becomes visible as the flesh-and-blood Empirical Author alongside her various collaborators in real life; second, she embodies the Model Author in her authorial personae that audiences find embedded in her films, blogging, and public self-fashioning; and finally as a performer, by starring as the main female protagonist in the films that she also directs. In a dynamic that is especially prominent in Xu Jinglei's case, but that one could equally identify in Li Jie's Anni Baobei/Qingshan, for instance (see above), the phenomenon of “Xu Jinglei” as a transmedia narrative relies on the connections and reflections between the Empirical Author, Model Author, and fictional characters that both modern celebrity culture and the interplay of the new and traditional commercial media facilitate.

Conclusion

Our analysis of Chinese cultural entrepreneurs has focused on their roles and ways of self-fashioning in a mediasphere that faces the two-fold pressure of state and market, characterised by a concentration of discursive power in the hands of commercial and political celebrities. The barriers and risks that organised movements and non-official opinion campaigns face in the country – especially since Xi Jinping's rise to the status of supreme leader during the last decade – invite us to think beyond the framework of propaganda versus dissent to understand how values, tastes, and lifestyles transform and

diversify in today's society. The investigation of cultural entrepreneurialism provides the conceptual tools and socio-historical perspectives to gain such insights, thus opening new paths to understanding cultural and ideological changes in twenty-first-century China.

As this study shows, cultural entrepreneurialism in Reform-era China first emerged as a deviation from socialist models of cultural production and consumption. Since the turn of the century, it has benefited from official policies aimed at developing culture as an industry and has been co-opted by the official discourse, which emphasises its economic rather than cultural dimensions. The definition of the cultural entrepreneur proposed in this article highlights their socio-political and ideological function instead. This study argues that, by altering and diversifying the cultural-ideological menu, cultural entrepreneurs can shape the tastes and values of those who consume both their cultural commodities and public personae as a mediatic product. In the context of Reform-era China, women rank among the most successful and innovative cultural entrepreneurs. Yet they also appear marginalised relative to the party-state's co-optation through the official media. Few of them feature in the official celebrations of China's cultural industries at the service of the party-state's policies. While the worldviews and lifestyles promoted by their products and personae are diversified and debated, as this study has shown, the very success of women cultural entrepreneurs challenges a resurgent emphasis on "traditional" gender roles in the official discourse.

This research has focused on three main case studies of women cultural entrepreneurs to identify and analyse three key dynamics at work in the cultural industries of twenty-first-century China. While it is difficult to generalise women's participation in the cultural economy in China on the basis of these very successful individuals, our analysis of their cases has shed light on such dynamics, while comparison with several other examples has placed them within their cultural context. First, Anni Baobei/Qingshan exemplifies how women cultural entrepreneurs navigate the complex connections between the traditional and digital media, which have replaced old hierarchies in both online and offline fields of practice. Second, artistic avant-gardism has become a function of market-oriented cultural entrepreneurialism, as Cao Fei's fusion of experimental art practice, corporate branding, and self-promotion shows. Third, by reflecting on the case of Xu Jinglei this study reveals how transmedia storytelling characterises the cultural entrepreneurs' cultural commodities while their personal brands constitute a new type of transmedia content. Both their media presence and cultural commodities construct a backstory and enhance a "core narrative" of values and lifestyles (Jenkins et al., 2013: 138), fusing Empirical Author, Model Author, and fictional characters for the audience's consumption. In this analysis, all three women cultural entrepreneurs appear as master storytellers.

In conclusion, this study has used a gendered approach to the figure of the cultural entrepreneur to conceptualise and shed new light on both the ideological and commercial dynamics of contemporary China's media and cultural industries. Further research may explore changes in the status, practices, and impact of China's cultural entrepreneurs in order to gain deeper insights into the transnational dimensions of cultural entrepreneurialism in contemporary China.

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